

Analysis of Supply Chain Management Practices in Stevedoring Business to Improve Operational Performance at PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa

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ABSTRACT: PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP) operates in the dynamic and competitive stevedoring industry, leveraging on its established brand, skilled workforce, strong operational strategy, and certifications such as ISO. This research explores new competitive dimensions for KJP through thematic analysis, PESTLE, Porter's Five Forces, and SWOT analysis. Using a qualitative research design, including in-depth interviews with internal and external stakeholders, the research identified opportunities and challenges facing KJP. The proposed vision is to become a leading and innovative stevedoring company by embracing digital transformation and sustainable practices. The key strategies proposed include improving operational efficiency, digital transformation, human resource development, expanding market reach, and strengthening customer relationships. The programmes formulated include process mapping, adoption of new technologies, employee training, market research, strategic partnerships, and customer relationship management (CRM) systems. The study also emphasised the importance of overcoming internal challenges such as reliance on manual processes, high dependence on key suppliers and customers, and resistance to change among senior employees. Recommendations include investment in advanced digital technologies, exploration of new markets, and promotion of sustainable practices to ensure long-term growth and competitiveness in the stevedoring industry. By aligning strategic objectives with the proposed vision, KJP aims to successfully navigate the competitive landscape and achieve sustainable growth.

KEYWORDS: Digital transformation, Human resource development, Loading and unloading, Marketing strategy, Operational efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The stevedoring industry, which is responsible for loading and unloading cargo from ships, has undergone significant changes driven by several factors such as privatisation-driven consolidation and the emergence of global terminal operators. One trend that stands out is the increasing vertical integration between global carriers and terminal operators, leading to a few major global players offering more efficient and cost-effective services. This shift is accompanied by an emphasis on efficiency and productivity, which spurs investment in advanced technology and equipment such as automated container handling systems and sophisticated cranes to streamline operations. In addition, there is a growing focus on sustainability and environmental responsibility, with initiatives aimed at reducing carbon emissions and implementing environmentally friendly practices such as using electric-powered equipment and optimising vessel schedules.

The stevedoring industry is vital to global maritime trade, including in Indonesia. Recent changes, including privatisation and the emergence of global terminal operators, have affected the structure of the industry, with vertical integration creating a divide between truly global players and regional players. Data from indices such as the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) and the International Transport Forum's Transport Competitiveness Index (TCI) highlight this dynamic, showing Singapore and the Netherlands as leaders due to their strong infrastructure and operational efficiency. For example, Singapore boasts the highest score of 8.4 out of 10 in the GCI for its highly developed loading and unloading operations, while the Netherlands scores 8.2 out of 10 for effective and efficient processes. The TCI reflects this trend, with Singapore's high score in cost competitiveness (7.9 out of 10) and the Netherlands' outstanding efficiency (8.1 out of 10). Globally, stevedoring capacity stands at around 1.4 billion TEUs per year, with significant contributions from countries such as China, the United States and Japan.

Indonesia faces challenges in terms of competitiveness in various sectors, including logistics performance and disparities between regions, which the government needs to address to improve overall competitiveness. Indonesia's national logistics performance ranks relatively low, coming in at 46th place in the Logistics Performance Index in 2018. This ranking is of concern to investors as logistics

costs can account for a significant portion of the total cost of goods. The tourism and creative economy sector, as measured by the Parekraf Index, shows regional variations, with some provinces, such as Sumatra and Sulawesi, having very low scores. This highlights the need for the central government to collaborate with local governments to improve these sectors. In addition, the Regional Competitiveness Index (RCI) has a significant positive impact on socioeconomic macroeconomic variables, such as Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) growth and Human Development Index (HDI), but a negative impact on the percentage of poor people.

In the highly competitive stevedoring industry, PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa faces significant challenges that are compounded by the evolving dynamics of global trade, technological advances, and increasing environmental regulations. Traditional competitive strategies based on cost and capacity are no longer adequate for long-term growth and profitability. Companies must explore new dimensions of competition, such as digital transformation, improved operational efficiency through advanced technologies, and sustainable practices. These new dimensions must be integrated into existing operations without disrupting ongoing activities or compromising service quality, while maintaining cost-effectiveness and operational flexibility.

The objectives of this research are to explore and identify potential alternative competitive dimensions for PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa to face current and future global business competition, to analyse and propose internal business process improvements to enhance operational efficiency, and to develop a comprehensive transformation roadmap that guides the company in achieving its short-term and long-term goals, ensuring sustainable growth and profitability. This research is very important because it addresses critical issues faced by PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa in the stevedoring industry. By identifying and proposing new competitive dimensions and improvements in internal business processes, this research aims to provide strategic insights that can improve the company's market position and operational efficiency.

The findings will contribute to the academic understanding of competitive strategy in the stevedoring industry and provide practical solutions for industry practitioners. The proposed transformation roadmap will guide PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa in achieving sustainable growth and profitability, which will ultimately benefit the wider field of logistics and maritime trade. Through this research, PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa will be better positioned to navigate the complex and rapidly changing global maritime trade landscape, ensuring long-term success and competitiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Competitiveness Theory*

Competitiveness theory explores the dynamics that enable regions, organisations, or economies to thrive in competitive scenarios, spanning multiple disciplines such as economics, business, and regional development. Originally focussed on economic indicators, contemporary interpretations now include non-economic factors such as innovation, sustainability, and quality of life (Silver, 1983). In the urban context, competitiveness incorporates infrastructure, technological advancement, and human capital, emphasising the role of cities as centres of creativity and innovation (Ietri & Kresl, 2014). At the regional level, the theory examines how geographical areas utilise unique attributes to compete effectively, with cohesive policies supporting innovation and infrastructure (University of Turin, 2010).

Various theories contribute to understanding competitiveness. Michael Porter's Diamond Model identifies four factors-factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy-that determine national competitiveness. The Resource-Based View (RBV) focuses on internal resources and capabilities as sources of competitive advantage. Cluster Theory emphasises the geographical concentration of firms to increase productivity and innovation. National and Global Competitiveness Theory analyses factors that affect competitiveness at the country level, including government policies and global value chains. Porter's Competitive Advantage Theory outlines strategies such as cost leadership, differentiation and focus for firms to achieve superior performance. Porter's frameworks, including the Diamond Model and the Theory of Competitive Advantage, are notable for their comprehensive and actionable insights into competitiveness. The Diamond Model analyses national competitive advantage through four key attributes, while the Theory of Competitive Advantage offers strategies for firms to achieve sustained superior performance (Porter, 1985). These theories are valued for their empirical rigour and practical applicability, guiding policymakers, business leaders and strategists in improving competitiveness at various scales. Porter's work on competitive advantage, despite

some criticism regarding its rigour and relevance in the modern business environment, continues to be widely applied and adapted in strategic management (Miller, 1992; Hax & Wilde, 2001).

B. Marketing Mix 7Ps

The 7Ps of Marketing Mix, an extension of the original 4P model, addresses the complexities of contemporary marketing and is particularly important in the service industry. Introduced by Booms and Bitner (1981) to include People, Process, and Physical Evidence, this framework recognises the shift towards service-oriented economic activity and the need for an inclusive approach that includes aspects of service delivery missed by traditional models. The extended model, which is widely discussed in the literature, emphasises the importance of each component in creating a cohesive marketing strategy (Rafiq & Ahmed, 1995). Each 'P' represents a fundamental aspect of marketing that firms must consider to effectively meet customer expectations and remain competitive.

In terms of Product, the literature underlines its evolution from mere physical goods to services, experiences and digital products, which requires marketers to be more innovative and responsive to market changes (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Pricing strategy not only includes competitive pricing, but also includes various pricing frameworks such as value-based, dynamic, and psychological pricing, which are influenced by economic factors and consumer purchasing power (Monroe, 2003). Place and Promotion have transformed significantly due to digitalisation, with Place now encompassing digital distribution channels and Promotion integrating digital and traditional media to create multi-channel communication campaigns (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Additional components, People, Process, and Physical Evidence, further refine marketing strategies. People focuses on the engagement and quality of human resources in marketing and service delivery, which is critical to customer satisfaction and brand perception. Process emphasises efficient business processes that support positive customer experiences, while Physical Evidence includes tangible elements that reinforce consumer trust, such as packaging, branding, and the environment in which products are delivered.

Marketing Mix 4.0, introduced by Kotler, Kartajaya, and Setiawan (2017), integrates traditional and digital marketing approaches to align with changing consumer behaviour in the digital era. This approach, built on the 7P framework (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, and Physical Evidence) emphasises the integration of digital strategies to improve marketing effectiveness. It introduces the 5A principles (Aware, Appeal, Ask, Act, Advocate) to map the consumer journey from awareness to advocacy, increasing brand engagement and driving business growth in the digital age. Recent research highlights the importance of integrating marketing capabilities to enhance competitive advantage and export performance. Qun Tan et al. (2015) provide empirical evidence that marketing capabilities significantly influence export performance by driving competitive advantages such as cost leadership and differentiation. Similarly, Vorhies et al. (2005) emphasise the benefits of benchmarking marketing capabilities among top-performing firms to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. Studies on SMEs, such as those by Fabrizio et al. (2021) and Papadas et al. (2019), show that dynamic capabilities and green marketing orientation can significantly improve the competitive position and financial performance of firms, reflecting the evolving nature of competitive advantage and the role of strategic flexibility in maintaining market leadership.

C. Business transformation and organizational transformation

Business transformation and organisational transformation are important concepts in the modern corporate landscape, addressing different but overlapping areas of change management and strategic renewal within companies. Business transformation refers to comprehensive change aimed at significantly improving performance and efficiency, driven by shifts in technology, market demand or the regulatory environment. It involves redefining business models, adopting new technologies, or entering different markets to ensure sustainability and competitiveness. Organisational transformation, on the other hand, focuses on internal aspects such as culture, structure, and employee behaviour. It supports business transformation by fostering a culture that is receptive to change, redesigning organisational structures to be more agile, and developing leadership and workforce capabilities. Both types of transformation are often triggered by external pressures such as technological advances and competitive threats, with digital transformation being a common example. Synergy between business and organisational transformation is essential; without the latter, business transformation can falter. Effective organisational transformation requires employee engagement through communication, training and involvement to ensure they support and execute the new strategy.

A quadripartite holistic approach, which includes process, technology, people and culture, integrates these elements to achieve sustainable organisational success. Business Process Management (BPM) emphasises structured processes supported by technology

and capabilities (Soltanifar et al., 2021). The adoption of technology, especially in the creative industries, enables innovative business models and operational efficiency (Li, 2018). Human capital is critical, with ongoing education and training able to upskill for more complex technologies (Dajah, 2022). Organisational culture, which includes shared values and behaviours, supports technology adoption and process alignment, improving overall effectiveness (Bate, Khan, & Pye, 2000). The transformation process begins with the Process phase, which involves idea generation, classification, and documentation to create a strategic plan (Smith & Taylor, 2020). The People phase aligns human resources with transformation goals, fostering a culture that is receptive to change (Johnson, 2021). The Tools phase selects technologies to support the transformation, and the Implementation phase integrates these elements through change management and blueprint creation (Kumar & Clark, 2022). This comprehensive approach ensures a smooth transition and continued success, making the organisation more responsive to market dynamics and effectively achieving strategic goals (Soltanifar et al., 2021).

D. Conceptual Framework

Creating a conceptual framework for transformation aimed at fostering new competitiveness involves strategically aligning organisational processes and resources towards innovation and market responsiveness. This framework starts with an Environmental Scan, using tools such as PESTEL and SWOT analyses to identify external opportunities and internal capabilities that require change, incorporating Competitive Theory to understand market dynamics and factors that influence competitiveness. This transitions into Vision and Strategy Formulation, where clear strategic objectives are set to improve competitiveness through cost leadership, differentiation and market focus. Organisational Alignment followed by restructuring the culture and processes, utilising Business & Organisational Transformation Theory and the 7P Marketing Mix framework to align the organisation's structure, culture and marketing strategy with the new direction.

The second phase emphasises practical implementation through Implementation and Execution, translating the strategic plan into actionable tasks using methodologies such as Agile or Lean. This is supported by Innovation and Continuous Improvement, ensuring the organisation remains adaptive through a continuous learning and innovation lab. Finally, Evaluation and Refinement enables regular assessment of transformation efforts, using performance indicators and feedback to refine the strategy. This holistic approach ensures effective implementation and ongoing alignment with market demands and internal growth objectives, thus maintaining long-term competitiveness. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework for the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

Research design is a methodical approach to problem solving and understanding, involving clear objectives and techniques to advance theory development, research, and practical applications (Salkind, 2010). This basic framework ensures that research is conducted methodologically and the results are reliable and analysed (Akhtar, 2016). For our research on developing a competitive strategy for PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa in the stevedoring industry, a qualitative approach was used, which offers flexibility and allows for in-depth exploration of subjective experiences (Creswell, 2014; Checkland, 1991). The research began with Business Problem Identification, thoroughly exploring the conditions affecting the company to determine the pressing issues. This was

followed by developing Research Objectives through a detailed literature review, identifying gaps, and establishing a clear research direction aligned with strategic business objectives. The Environmental Scan phase utilised PESTEL and SWOT analyses, incorporating the Theory of Competition to understand the market landscape and internal/external factors impacting competitiveness. The Develop Vision & Strategy phase then sets clear strategic objectives focused on cost leadership, differentiation, and market focus, guided by strategic management and competitive advantage theory.

Organisational Alignment is critical, which involves restructuring culture and processes using Business & Organisational Transformation Theory and the 7P Marketing Mix framework. Finally, Programme Formulation & Implementation Plan translates the strategic plan into actionable tasks, supported by Agile or Lean methodologies for flexible and efficient implementation. Continuous improvement ensures the organisation remains adaptive and forward-thinking. This comprehensive approach systematically engages stakeholders, ensuring that transformation efforts are implemented effectively and aligned with evolving market demands and internal growth objectives, driving sustainable development within the stevedoring sector. The research design of this study is shown in Figure 2.

B. Data Collection

Interviews were the main data collection method in this study, which were conducted in two rounds as outlined in the Research Design. The first round aimed to identify an unstructured problem situation, while the second round focused on critical validation of the proposed strategy to ensure feasibility, describe roles and responsibilities, and design an effective implementation strategy. Key participants include internal stakeholders from PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa, such as the General Manager, Operations Manager, Finance Manager, HR Manager, and Marketing Manager, who have insights that are critical for effective strategy formulation and sustainable business development. For the second round, the General Manager will be involved to define the project structure and strategic direction. External stakeholders, including local government (PEMDA) representatives and key customers, will also be interviewed to provide valuable insights into industry trends, challenges and opportunities. Interviews will address strategic rationale, operational insights, financial expectations, human resources, market trends, and environmental sustainability, tailored to specific stakeholder types. This comprehensive set of questions aims to gather detailed and actionable insights, ensuring a thorough understanding of the current situation and identifying opportunities for strategic improvement.

Figure 2. Research Design

C. Data Analysis

The data analysis for this study used qualitative methods, specifically focusing on thematic analysis, to develop a new performance management system using goal setting theory (Travers et al., 2015). Qualitative methods are effective in extracting and utilising experts' tacit knowledge to build performance models, which offer a deep understanding of complex systems (Cohanier, 2014). This approach begins with familiarisation, where the researcher immerses themselves in the data to gain a deep understanding of its content. This is followed by creating initial codes, which systematically categorise segments of data relevant to the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2006). These codes were then organised into potential themes, reviewed and refined to ensure that they formed coherent patterns that accurately reflected the data set, culminating in a comprehensive report. To complement the thematic analysis, Porter's Five Forces Analysis will be used to examine the competitive environment of PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa. This tool analyses the competitive rivalry, threat of new entrants, threat of substitute products, and bargaining power of suppliers and buyers (Porter, 2008; Yunna & Yisheng, 2014). By creating a five forces diagram, the research identified key competitive pressures and opportunities in the stevedoring industry, providing a strategic overview that informed the development of the company's vision and strategy.

Based on insights from thematic analysis and the Five Forces, a SWOT analysis will systematically identify internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats for PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (Gürel & Tat, 2017). This analysis will use data from interviews and focus group discussions to populate the SWOT table, so as to help understand the company's internal capabilities and external environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Thematic Analysis

PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP) faces various challenges and opportunities in maintaining and improving its position in the stevedoring industry. The thematic analysis of the interviews shows that strategic planning and strong business management are essential. For example, the Managing Director explained, "For joining PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa.... My tasks here as the Managing Director involve... developing and achieving future business plans." Key roles and responsibilities at KJP focus on developing and achieving future business plans, sustaining growth, and capitalising on natural resources for business opportunities, as expressed, "Kutai Jaya Pundinusa and particularly Samarinda have business potentials... mainly in natural resources." Strategic planning at KJP includes setting budgets, operational strategies, and marketing plans, with a particular focus on pricing and service. "We have set budgets, operational strategies, and marketing plans... especially in pricing and services."

Effective financial management ensures cash flow stability and profitability, as mentioned, "In finance, cash flow is running... and eventually, profits are achieved." Organisational development is essential, with an emphasis on promoting managers and enhancing human resources through continuous training and development, as explained, "Organisational development and regeneration... enhancing and promoting managers in marketing." The company also places importance on relationship management, maintaining good relationships with customers and government, and ensuring good corporate governance through internal audits, "Maintaining good relationships with customers, government, and good corporate governance." However, internal challenges such as resistance to change among senior employees and communication issues need to be addressed, "Our main internal challenge is the mindset of senior employees, particularly those above 40, who have a mental block against change." Soft skills enhancement, leadership training, and effective internal communication are essential for organisational development, "We need to enhance soft skills among employees... focusing more on leadership and communication training."

Competitively, KJP faces significant challenges from local and regional competitors. Local stevedoring companies have an advantage due to familiarity and regional connections, while companies like Penascope provide competition at the national level, "If we talk about competitors, especially in Samarinda, the competitors are mostly local stevedoring companies. These local companies have an edge because they are familiar with the region, they can easily manoeuvre due to their local connections, and they sometimes get preferential treatment due to local regulations." To remain competitive, KJP needs to focus on digital transformation, improve internal communication, and possibly restructure the organisation for better operational efficiency. "One key improvement area is the digitalisation of our processes. For example, our current process for handling permits is manual, leading to inefficiencies. Implementing a digital system to manage and alert us about permit expirations can significantly improve efficiency."

Strategic goals for KJP include stabilising cash flow, expanding market reach, and investing in human resources and technology infrastructure, "Our short-term goal is to stabilise our cash flow and ensure all departments are working efficiently. This involves strict monitoring and regular evaluations to catch any potential issues early." Digital transformation and maintaining relationships with vendors for quality service is critical, "Emphasize on digital transformation... maintain relationships with vendors... ensuring quality service and equipment." The company also needs to address the impact of regulations and maintain high service standards through continuous improvement, "The impact of regulations can be positive or negative... positive regulations like PTB can add profit... we adjust to the regulations for improvement."

KJP's competitive advantage is strengthened by the Samudera brand, ISO certification, and a skilled workforce, "KJP has the goodwill of the Samudera brand... follows ISO certification... has very skilled and solid workers." Daily monitoring and preventive measures help maintain business continuity and improve the work environment, "We always do daily monitoring, so the obstacles or challenges that exist are always taken preventive measures... making the business process not fail or break down... challenges make the work environment better." Leadership by example and transparency in communication are emphasised to align performance with company goals, "As a leader, I have to set an example for the team... systematic procedures, how we build communication with the team... and openness." A comprehensive marketing strategy, incorporating the 7Ps, ensures that the service meets customer needs through competitive pricing, good service, and effective promotion, "The 7Ps marketing mix is crucial to our strategy... implementing it effectively across all aspects of our business ensures we meet customer needs and stay competitive."

"Market research plays a crucial role in our strategic planning... we conduct marketing intelligence and business intelligence to understand the market and our position within it." KJP also faces internal challenges such as a lean organisational structure that sometimes hampers operational efficiency. "The structure of our organisation is quite lean, which sometimes hampers our ability to perform efficiently. Having more dedicated personnel for specific roles can help in better management and operational efficiency." As such, KJP needs to consider organisational restructuring to improve operational efficiency. "KJP's advantage is having the authority to make decisions quickly without needing approval from the central office... this allows for faster response times and better customer service." In addition, technology adaptation, particularly in automation and digitalisation, is a key focus to maintain competitive advantage, "Technology advancements, particularly in automation and digitalisation, can significantly impact our business model... we must stay adaptive and integrate these advancements to maintain our competitive edge."

A comprehensive marketing strategy using the 7Ps framework is key in ensuring that the services provided meet customer needs and remain competitive in the market, "The 7Ps marketing mix is crucial to our strategy... implementing it effectively across all aspects of our business ensures we meet customer needs and stay competitive." "It is essential to maintain a balance between market intelligence and internal business intelligence... understanding both external market trends and internal capabilities helps us plan strategically." Employee development is an important aspect in improving operational efficiency and competitiveness, with a focus on continuous training and adoption of industry best practices, "Improving operational efficiency and competitiveness involves continuous HR development, leveraging digital tools, and adopting industry best practices... ensuring all employees are motivated to enhance their skills and contribute to the company's success." As such, this thematic analysis provides a detailed roadmap for KJP's strategic and operational focus, highlighting the importance of addressing internal challenges, leveraging digital transformation, and maintaining strong relationships with stakeholders to ensure competitiveness and long-term growth in the stevedoring industry.

B. Environmental Scanning

To comprehensively understand the external and internal factors affecting PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP), an environmental scanning process is required. This process includes PESTLE analysis to assess political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors; Porter's Five Forces analysis to evaluate competitive pressures in the industry; and SWOT analysis to identify the company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. These analyses provide a holistic view of the external environment and internal capabilities, guide strategic decision-making, and ensure KJP remains competitive and resilient in the stevedoring industry. Firstly, PESTLE analysis was used to identify and understand the various external factors affecting KJP's operations.

- Political, regulations from the Ministry of Transportation and local governance can have a positive or negative impact on KJP's operations. KJP also emphasises good corporate governance through internal audits and compliance with regulatory standards, "Compliance with government regulations such as those from the Ministry of Transportation, which can have both positive and negative effects on operations."

- Economy, significant market opportunities, especially in the natural resources sector such as in Samarinda. Effective financial management, competitive pricing, and strategic cost management are important to ensure economic resilience and growth, "Significant business opportunities, especially in the natural resources sector in areas like Samarinda."
- Social, human resource development through continuous training and a culture of open communication as well as enhancement of leadership skills and soft skills among employees is essential, "Investment in employee training and development to enhance skills and ensure alignment with evolving business needs."
- Technology, implementation of digital systems for process efficiency such as permit management and adoption of new technologies such as automation to maintain competitive advantage. A comprehensive marketing strategy using the 7Ps (product, price, place, promotion, people, process, physical evidence) ensures that KJP remains competitive and customer-focused, "Implementation of digital systems for processes like permit management to improve efficiency."
- Environment, compliance with environmental regulations and adoption of sustainable practices are important for long-term operational viability, "Ensuring that operations, especially in natural resource extraction, adhere to environmental regulations and sustainability practices."
- Legal, adapting to changes in regulations and managing contracts and relationships with vendors and customers to ensure legal compliance and protect business interests, "Adapting to changes in regulations and ensuring that all business activities comply with local and national laws."

Furthermore, Porter's Five Forces analysis helps evaluate the competitive pressures in the stevedoring industry, identifying the forces that affect KJP's competitiveness:

- Competitive Rivalry, KJP faces high competition from local and national stevedoring companies with strong regional connections, "High level of competition from local stevedoring companies and national firms with local connections."
- Threat of New Entrants, high barriers to entry due to large capital investment and complex local regulations. KJP's brand loyalty is also a barrier to new entrants, "Moderate to high, mainly due to the need for substantial capital investment and local regulations."
- Strength of Supplier Bids, high dependence on vendors for essential equipment and services, but KJP maintains strong relationships with suppliers to ensure quality and reliability, "High dependence on vendors for equipment and services, impacting operational efficiency."
- Buyer Bid Power, high dependency on key customers, especially in natural resource sectors, with high price sensitivity, "High dependency on key customers, especially in natural resource sectors."
- Threat of Substitute Products, moderate threat from technological advancements such as automation that could reduce the need for traditional stevedoring services, "Moderate threat from automation and digitalisation in stevedoring operations."

Finally, the SWOT analysis provides a comprehensive view of KJP's strategic position, identifying internal factors that affect the company's capabilities.

- Strengths, established brand with goodwill (Samudera), strong operational strategies and marketing plans, skilled and solid workforce, ISO certifications, quick decision making, and effective communication and relationship management, "Established brand with goodwill (Samudera), strong operational strategies and marketing plans, skilled and solid workforce, ISO certifications."
- Weaknesses, dependence on manual processes in some areas, high reliance on key suppliers and customers, lean organisational structure, resistance to change among senior employees, and limited presence in social media and digital marketing, "Dependence on manual processes in some areas, high reliance on key suppliers and customers, lean organisational structure."
- Opportunities, digital transformation and automation to improve efficiency, expansion into national and international markets, diversification of products and services, strategic partnerships with global companies, and participation in national logistics systems, "Digital transformation and automation to improve efficiency, expansion into national and international markets, diversification of product offerings and services."
- Threats, intense competition from local and national stevedoring companies, regulatory changes, economic fluctuations affecting the natural resources sector, technological advances that may disrupt traditional business models, and potential

entry of new competitors with large capital and local connections, "Intense competition from local and national stevedoring companies, regulatory changes that may impact operations."

With an in-depth understanding of this environmental analysis, KJP can develop strategies to capitalise on opportunities and address potential risks in the stevedoring industry, ensuring that the company remains competitive and grows sustainably.

C. Develop Vision & Strategy

Developing a comprehensive vision and strategy for PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP) required a thorough evaluation of the company's internal and external environment, as identified through thematic analysis, PESTLE, Porter's Five Forces, and SWOT. This evaluation highlighted KJP's strengths such as an established brand, skilled workforce, strong operational strategy, and certifications such as ISO. In addition, KJP's ability to make quick decisions and maintain effective communication and relationship management positioned the company well in the competitive stevedoring industry. However, KJP faces significant challenges, including reliance on manual processes, high dependence on key suppliers and customers, and a lean organisational structure that sometimes hampers efficiency. Resistance to change among senior employees and limited use of social media and digital marketing complicate its operational landscape. Nevertheless, KJP has many opportunities to capitalise on, such as digital transformation, market expansion, product and service diversification, and strategic partnerships. Threats from intense competition, regulatory changes, economic fluctuations, and technological advancements require a proactive and adaptive strategic approach.

To guide KJP towards sustainable growth and competitiveness in the stevedoring industry, a clear vision and concrete strategic objectives are essential. The proposed vision statement for PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa is: "To be a leading and innovative stevedoring company, embracing digital transformation and sustainable practices, while expanding our market reach nationally and internationally, and continuously enhancing our workforce's skills and operational efficiency." Its strategic objectives include: digital transformation to improve operational efficiency, national and international market expansion to diversify revenue streams, product and service diversification to reduce the risk of dependence on a single source of revenue, human capital development to enhance employee skills and capabilities, enhanced communications and digital marketing to increase visibility and brand loyalty, and compliance and sustainability to ensure operations adhere to international standards and local regulations. By aligning its strategic objectives with the proposed vision, KJP aims to successfully navigate the competitive landscape, overcome current challenges, and capitalize on emerging opportunities, ensuring competitiveness and long-term growth in the stevedoring industry.

D. Business Process

To understand how PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP) manages its loading and unloading operations, which is its core business, this study uses a Holistic Quadruple approach that includes the dimensions of Process, Technology, People, and Organisational Culture (Figure 3). This approach ensures that every aspect of operations is considered thoroughly and integrated, improving efficiency and effectiveness.

Figure 3. Business Process of Stevedoring Operations

- Process, KJP's loading and unloading operations begin with order management from clients. The order management team receives and confirms the order details to ensure the client's needs are met. After order confirmation, the next stage is planning and scheduling, including allocation of resources such as labour and equipment required. At the execution stage, the cargo is loaded and unloaded as per the set schedule with close supervision to avoid disruptions. Inspections are conducted to ensure the quality of cargo handling. After the operation is completed, an operational report is generated for the client and used for internal review, including post-operation analysis and feedback for service improvement.
- Technology, technology plays an important role in supporting operational processes at KJP. A digital order management system is used to process and track orders, integrated with client systems for seamless communication. Automated scheduling software helps in scheduling labour and equipment, allowing real-time adjustments as per operational needs. IoT and sensors are used for real-time monitoring during execution, and automated equipment such as cranes improve cargo handling efficiency. Digital quality control tools ensure consistent inspections and automated reports for quality checks. Reporting software uses data analytics tools to generate comprehensive reports stored in the cloud.
- People, the key to successful loading and unloading operations at KJP is a competent team. The order management team consists of skilled professionals who handle client communication and order processing. The planning and scheduling team are experts in logistics planning and resource allocation. The operations team is trained in loading and unloading cargo, working under the supervision of supervisors who ensure plans are properly executed. The quality control team consists of experienced inspectors who ensure quality standards are met. The reporting team involves data analysts who ensure operational information is presented accurately and on time.
- Organisational Culture, the organisational culture at KJP emphasises collaboration and communication, encouraging teamwork and communication between departments. Open channels for feedback and suggestions reinforce the spirit of togetherness. KJP also prioritises continuous improvement, encouraging innovation and process optimisation through regular training and development programmes. Accountability and transparency are maintained with clearly defined roles and responsibilities and transparent reporting. Customer focus is at the core of KJP's culture with a commitment to meet and exceed client expectations through regular feedback and strong relationship management.

Here, PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa ensures that every aspect of loading and unloading operations is considered and optimised. This includes efficient processes, advanced technology, a competent team, and a strong organisational culture, all geared towards achieving high operational efficiency, client satisfaction, and sustainable business growth.

E. Program Formulation

In order to achieve the vision and strategy of PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP), programme formulation is an important step that must be done carefully. The programme will focus on improving operational efficiency, digital transformation, human resource development, expanding market reach, and strengthening customer relationships.

Operational efficiency improvement starts with process mapping to understand each workflow in loading and unloading operations, identify bottlenecks, and apply lean principles to reduce waste and improve efficiency. The use of performance metrics will facilitate continuous monitoring and measurement of operational efficiency. Furthermore, digital transformation involves assessing existing technologies to identify improvement needs and opportunities, developing a comprehensive digital strategy, integrating existing systems with new technologies, and training employees to improve digital skills and accelerate technology adoption in daily operations.

Human Capital Development is focused on skills gap analysis to identify areas for improvement, design of appropriate training programmes, introduction of leadership development programmes, and periodic performance reviews to ensure employee development is aligned with company objectives and provide constructive feedback for performance improvement. Meanwhile, market reach expansion is a strategic step to enhance KJP's business growth and sustainability. The first step is to conduct in-depth market research to identify new market opportunities at the national and international levels. Based on the research results, KJP will develop effective marketing strategies to attract new customers and strengthen relationships with existing customers. Strategic partnerships with other companies will be formed to expand the customer base and increase market share. Sales team expansion will be undertaken to increase the capacity to handle increased market demand and ensure KJP can respond to market opportunities quickly and effectively.

Finally, strengthening customer relations starts with listening to feedback from customers to understand their needs and expectations. Based on this feedback, KJP will organise customer service training to improve the quality of interactions with customers. The use of a customer relationship management (CRM) system will be implemented to facilitate the management of customer data and improve service. In addition, a customer loyalty programme will be introduced to ensure long-term customer satisfaction and retention, and strengthen the relationship between KJP and its customers. Through the formulation of this programme, PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa is committed to improving operational efficiency, accelerating digital transformation, developing human resources, expanding market reach, and strengthening customer relationships. With a structured approach that focuses on these important aspects, KJP is poised to achieve its vision and strategic goals and ensure sustainable growth and strong competitiveness in the stevedoring industry.

CONCLUSION

PT Kutai Jaya Pundinusa (KJP) operates in the dynamic and competitive stevedoring industry, leveraging its established brand, skilled workforce, strong operational strategy, and certifications such as ISO to build a solid foundation for growth. However, the company faces internal challenges, including reliance on manual processes, high dependence on key suppliers and customers, and resistance to change among senior employees. To address these challenges, KJP's comprehensive strategic plan focuses on improving operational efficiency, implementing digital transformation, developing human resources, expanding market reach, and strengthening customer relationships. By conducting thorough process mapping and applying lean principles, KJP aims to streamline operations and remove bottlenecks. Digital transformation is critical to improving operational accuracy and responsiveness, supported by the integration of advanced technology and a comprehensive employee training programme. Human capital development remains a priority, with continued investment in training and leadership initiatives. Expanding market reach through strategic partnerships and effective marketing strategies will diversify revenue sources, while strengthening customer relationships through feedback mechanisms, customer service training and loyalty programmes will ensure long-term satisfaction and retention. A robust monitoring and evaluation framework, including KPIs, review meetings, feedback mechanisms and regular reporting, fosters a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation, thereby promoting long-term success and sustainability in the competitive stevedoring industry.

To ensure KJP's continued growth and competitiveness, it is recommended that the company prioritise investment in advanced digital equipment and automation technology, enhance training programmes to foster a culture of innovation, and actively explore new markets through in-depth research and strategic partnerships. In addition, strengthening customer relationships by implementing a robust CRM system and developing customer loyalty programmes will help maintain strong relationships with customers. KJP should also continue to comply with environmental regulations and promote sustainable practices, optimise resource use, reduce carbon emissions, and implement effective waste management strategies. By fulfilling these recommendations, KJP can improve its competitive position, achieve sustainable growth, and ensure long-term success in the stevedoring industry.

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